

Financial Technology and Allied Areas with reference to Bachelors Program: An International Look

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Abstract

Financial technology is also called as FinTech, it is a new [technology](#) which is responsible for the modernization of traditional financial methods into different way and with computing enabled [financial services](#). FinTech sector is currently using technology which helps in promotion of activities in finance and other affairs. The [smart phones](#) is used for different affairs and these led the concept of [mobile banking](#), [investing services](#). Currently, crypto currency is emerging rapidly and there are many examples of technologies for better and sophisticated financial services. Financial technology companies are moving towards better and healthy initiatives in promotion of [startups](#) and establishments are trying to better financial services. Information Technology tools plays a lead role for Financial technology field development both in practice and academically. Today many universities have started program and degrees in this field with name of Financial Technology, Financial Business Technology Financial Computing etc. The goal of this kind of program is to provide and generate knowledge as well as skills which are emerging in financial technology sector. Fintech is responsible for the great changes in traditional banks and insurance companies. The product/skilled in this field will taught innovation management techniques and they will be able to design as well as implement software applications, importantly here the data analytic, big data. Cloud computing, machine learning etc skills are required by new data driven models of financial services promotion and development. This paper is conceptual and theoretical in nature and talks about the basics of financial technology including its features, characteristics, development and function as a whole. The paper also emphasized about the program in this field and program potentiality in brief.

Keywords: Information Technology, Business, Education, Financial Technology, Development, Market, BSc Financial Technology

Introduction

Financial Technology is an important aspect of modern age and called FinTech. This is the applications of IT and Computing in Financial areas and field. This is important to empower the financial services and over traditional financial services. Financial Technology is also a new sector which lies on different kind of technology and devices viz. computers, smart phones and mobile phones [1], [5]. Today financial company and other organizations are using this technology for advanced and modern financial services. Financial Technology may be used in different other areas viz.

- Automate Insurance
- Advanced Trading
- Insurance and Risk Management as well.

Financial Technology is the new applications, processes, products and also business models in the financial services and banking services. The market of Financial Technology is emerging rapidly and financial technology increased more than 2,200% from \$930 million in 2008 to more than \$22 billion in 2015. It is worthy to note that according to the latest study it is noted that about 40% manpower in London are engaged in Financial and allied sectors. It is important that, Financial Technology organizations and university's these days are putting efforts to bring skilled and solid manpower in this field and as a result.

Objective

The core aim and agenda of this paper is include but not limited to the following—

- To know basic about Financial Technology including its meaning and features in brief manner.
- To learn about the basic importance of Financial Technology and allied areas in concise manner.
- To learn about the Bachelors educational programs available in the field of Financial Technology in international universities.
- To know about the educational programs possible and easy to start in Indian Universities based on Indian education systems.
- To learn about the basic course gradients in Financial Technology at Bachelors level as per result.

Methodology

The current study is review type and deals with the study of review of literature. It is also associated with study of web review and higher educational directory search and importantly web review of curriculum and syllabus of the Financial Technology at bachelors level. Simple Google search engine search strategy has been used with the tag 'Bachelors Degree in Financial Technology' and from there appropriate programs have been selected.

Financial Technology

Financial Technology, in short FinTech is a technology and area responsible for designing and development of financial system which is supported by the computing and information technology for doing financial and allied affairs [2], [3]. It is also leading the concept of emerging and automated financial services to promote healthy and wealthy banking and financial activities. Day by day the technology applications are rising and, in this category, most emerging are include—

- Big Data
- Data Analytics
- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Cloud Computing
- Data Security
- Virtualization etc

It is also worthy to note that, various banking and financial service related affairs also been associated with the Financial Technology [7].

Career opportunities and Financial Technology as a Field of Study

Financial Technology or Fintech is an emerging field and growing sector and there are numerous opportunities across exciting and new start-up companies in the field and areas of banking and insurance etc [4], [8].

In European scenario, London is treated as the fintech hub and various jobs are created in recent past. It is also important to note that, Edinburgh is also a leading and largest city in terms of fintech opportunities and various initiatives have been undertaken for improving Scottish fintech sector. It is also important to expect that it will continue to grow radically over the coming years.

Financial Technology is actually the mix of computing, analytics and business skills and thus apart from Financial areas traditional data science jobs may also possible to grab by the candidates. Students of the field can pursue jobs in different areas viz. banks, the NHS, marketing companies, private companies, the oil industry, and in government etc apart from private companies [6], [10].

It is concerned with the use of technology and computing to make financial transactions more efficient and healthy interaction and knowledge in the field of finance, accounting, business information systems and analytic methods are highly required to become a solid and sophisticated human resource in this field and domain.

As, Financial Technology programs comes with the fundamentals of Accounting & Finance and Management Science thus the skilled manpower in this field can also go for the position like teaching and research. Most of the universities offers the program in the field from the candidates coming from variety of background but who want a career in this emerging area.

It is important to note that, comprehensive skill set including combines theory, intensive practice and industrial engagement are most important and valuable in Financial Technology; moreover new technologies have been also associated to innovate and streamline financial systems.

Various areas such as Blockchain, Cryptocurrency, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence and Bots, Internet of Things and Big Data etc become course gradients in Financial Technology program and importantly highly applicable in different sectors and place and competitive technology-driven world. Internationally many universities have started program at Bachelors level in Financial Technology and few of these are depicted in Table: 1 according to the adopted study [4], [9].

Table: 1 Depicted the Financial Technology programs at Bachelors level at International University

Sl. No.	Name of the Program	Institute/ University	Country
1	BSc-Financial Technology Management	Glyndwr University	United Kingdom
2	BSc (H)-Financial Technology	The Hong Kong Polytechnic University	China
3	BSc (H)-Financial Computing	University of Liverpool	United Kingdom
4	BSc (H)- Business Financial Technology	Falmouth University	United Kingdom
5	BE-Financial Technology	The Chinese University of Hong Kong	China
6	BS- Financial Technology	Virginia Commonwealth University	United States

Moreover, in details course curriculum has been provided in Table: 2 comprises with the areas of Banking and finance, Technology, Commerce and Management [11-14].

Table: 2- Masters program in Digital Business in International Universities: Curricula Highlights

Universities	Papers/ Courses
BSc (H)-Financial Technology, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University	Programming for FinTech Applications Computer Systems Security Business Finance E Payment and Crypto currency Crowdfunding and E Finance Big Data Analytics Emerging Topics in FinTech
BSc (H)- Business Financial Technology, Falmouth University	Driving Operations Marketing Intelligence Innovation and Improvisation Financial Insight Effective Marketing and Sales Understanding and Influencing People Data Storytelling International Market Team Leadership and performance Mining Big Data Risk, ethics and Environment Transformational Leadership Creative Strategies Business Challenges Data Innovation Professional Practice
BSc-Financial Technology Management, Glyndwr University	Business Idea Generation Business Communication for Skill Marketing Economics Business and Finance in Practice Marketing Essentials Data Analytics and Understanding Big Data Innovation Commercialization Engaging and Leading People Advertising and Branding Enabling Technologies and Business Opportunities in Finance Strategic Thinking Disruptive Innovation and Financial Technologies

	Business Sustainability and Growth Dissertation/ Project/ Placement-Internship (all)
BSc (H)-Financial Computing, University of Liverpool	Introduction to the Programming Programming Language Paradigms Digital Society Analytics Techniques for the Computer Science Object Oriented Programming Introduction to Financial Account Introduction to the Management Account Principle of Microeconomics Software Engineering Database Development E Commerce Group Project Computer based training in Financial Markets Securities Market Quantitative Business Finance Finance and Markets Technologies for E Commerce Introduction to the Computational Game Theory (Optional Electives are offered in Second & Third Year)

India and Financial Technology: The Academic Perspective

India is a developing nation and growing rapidly. India hold a large number of educational institutes in the world. At present India hold about 40000+ institutes and among these 800+ are tagged as universities (the category wise listed in Table: 3). But important to note that degrees and diplomas in this field is very minimum and better to say absent. But the program may be offered either as full-fledged degree like BSc/MSc in Financial Technology or in Engineering platform as BTech/MTech in Financial Technology.

Table: 3- Universities in India: A Snapshot

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Central Universities	47	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	370	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	290	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	123	Except some states and UT

It is worthy to note that the degrees may be offered as specializations in other related and allied degrees viz. here few proposed areas are Commerce, Management and Computer Applications.

Table: 4 Proposed Financial Technology program

Sl. No.	Possible Bachelors Program (Commerce Track)	Possible Masters Program (Commerce Track)	Possible Masters Program (Computer Applications)
1	BBA/ BBM (Financial Technology)	MBA/ MMA (Financial Technology)	BCA/ MCA (Financial Technology)
2	BBA/ BBM (Digital Finance and Big Data)	MBA/ MMA (Digital Finance and Big Data)	BCA/ MCA (Digital Finance and Big Data)
3	BBA/ BBM (Financial Engineering)	MBA/ MMA (Financial Engineering)	BCA/ MCA (Financial Engineering)

Conclusion

Financial technology is useful in both startups and also already existing and established financial as well technology companies engaged in financial services A study conducted by the KPMG, only Sydney's financial services sector in the year 2017 creates 9 % of national GDP. It is worthy to note that such financial benefits and growth even bigger than the financial services offered in Hong Kong or even Singapore. Proper and healthy manpower creation is highly solicited in Financial Technology sector to gear-up and build healthy Financial systems of an organization, and even whole territory. Universities and institutes are today offering different kind of programs in Digital Finance and Financial Technologies the developing countries may opt the option of specialization instead of full-fledged degrees.

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